

Corporate Preferences for Forest Carbon Offsets in Spain: Evidence from Firms Within and Beyond a Voluntary Climate Disclosure Registry

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Abstract

Firms are increasingly turning to voluntary carbon markets to offset emissions as part of their net-zero strategies. However, the factors shaping corporate motivations, behavioural drivers, and preferences for carbon offsets have received limited academic attention. Drawing on the Theory of Planned Behaviour and integrating it with a Discrete Choice Experiment, this study examines the behavioural and preferences-based factors influencing Spanish firms' decisions to offset greenhouse gas emissions through forest-based carbon removal projects. The analysis compares firms participating in the Carbon Footprint Registry, a government-led voluntary mechanism for climate disclosure and mitigation efforts, with firms operating outside formal disclosure frameworks. The results indicate that, for Registry firms, subjective norms, particularly stakeholder expectations and competitor behaviour, together with positive internal attitudes, constitute the main drivers of offsetting behaviour. In contrast, non-registered firms' decisions are driven primarily by perceived control, economic considerations, and peer influence, with attitudes playing a more limited role. The findings further highlight the importance of awareness of climate disclosure mechanisms and carbon market functioning, as firms with higher levels of awareness exhibit a significantly greater propensity to engage in carbon offsetting. Taken together, the findings indicate that expanding voluntary carbon market participation requires policy and institutional designs that account for firm heterogeneity, strengthen organisational capacity, and foster positive internal attitudes towards offsetting, particularly among smaller and less engaged firms.

Keywords: Theory of Planned Behaviour, PLS-SEM, Discrete Choice Experiment, Carbon Removal, Survey, Corporate Climate Strategies.

JEL: Q50, Q56.

1 Introduction

Achieving the Paris Agreement goal requires the progressive decarbonisation of economies. To facilitate this transition, governments have introduced carbon pricing mechanisms, including market-based instruments such as emissions trading systems (ETSs) and regulatory approaches such as carbon taxes (World Bank, 2025). In parallel, voluntary carbon markets (VCMs) have developed through the initiative of private actors and standard-setting institutions, providing a complementary avenue for advancing net-zero pathways (Ruiting et al., 2025). Within VCMs, firms, organisations, and investors purchase carbon credits to compensate for their emissions by supporting activities that either avoid GHG emissions or remove CO₂ from the atmosphere through technological and nature-based solutions (Fawzy et al., 2020; Probst et al., 2024).

Among these, forests play a particularly prominent role. They act as a sink for CO₂ while also becoming a major source of emissions when deforestation and degradation occur (Harris et al., 2021). This dual capacity underpins their integration into carbon markets through forest carbon offsets (FCOs), which cover both avoided emissions and CO₂ removals (Roe et al., 2019). FCOs are often considered relatively accessible and cost-effective compared to other mitigation options (Grafton et al., 2021; Busch et al., 2024), offering a means to address hard-to-abate residual emissions (IPCC, 2022) while simultaneously delivering biodiversity and other co-benefits (Lee et al., 2018). Reflecting this importance, forest-based projects¹ account for nearly one-third of all credits issued under the main voluntary carbon market standards (Haya et al., 2025).

Firms are central actors in climate action under the Paris Agreement, both through their direct mitigation commitments and their participation in regulatory and market-based instruments (Evro et al., 2024; Wright and Nyberg, 2024). As the main participants in VCMs and the primary buyers of FCOs (Xie and Chen, 2025), their engagement depends on the availability of certification systems that establish the credibility and tradability of offsets. International standards such as Verra’s Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) and the Gold Standard currently dominate global markets (Haya et al., 2025), while many domestic schemes have emerged to reflect national approaches to voluntary carbon accounting and offsetting (Cevallos et al., 2019). In Spain, this role is fulfilled by the Carbon Footprint Registry (hereafter, the Registry), a government-led national mechanism for voluntary climate disclosure, emissions reduction tracking, and offsetting efforts (MITECO, 2024).

However, corporate participation in the Registry remains marginal when measured against the overall business landscape in Spain. Between 2008 and 2024, only 6,055 organisations and individuals registered their carbon footprint at least once, of which 91% were private firms (77% small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and 14% large firms). These entities represent less than 0.2% of all active firms in Spain (INE, 2024), and only about 8% of participants have gone further to actively offset emissions through domestic projects, currently limited to afforestation, reforestation, and post-wildfire restoration. Yet, despite this very limited uptake in terms of firm numbers, the Registry captures a substantial share of emissions: reported Scope 1 and 2 emissions account for around 20% in 2019–2022, reflecting the strong concentration of emissions among a small number of large firms (Ovando, 2025). This combination of low participation and high emissions coverage raises fundamental questions about the psychological and economic motivations shaping firms’ engagement with forest carbon offsetting, and whether these motivations differ systematically between firms already engaged in disclosure and mitigation frameworks and those that remain outside them.

Whereas consumer attitudes towards carbon offsetting have been widely studied (e.g.,

¹These include Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD), Improved Forest Management (IFM), and Afforestation and Reforestation (AR) projects.

Blasch and Farsi, 2014; Ritchie et al., 2021; Haug and Hassinggaard, 2023; Warburg et al., 2021; Schleich and Alsheimer, 2024), research on corporate attitudes and preferences for participation in voluntary carbon markets remains comparatively scarce, although recent work is beginning to fill this gap through varied and complementary research designs. Lou et al. (2023), analysing data from 186 corporations across multiple countries through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reports and Carbon Disclosure Project questionnaires, categorise corporate motivations to participate in VCMs into cost-efficient carbon management, market competitiveness, and corporate values, with sectoral variation further confirmed by market assessments (Donofrio et al., 2021; Xie and Chen, 2025).

The most comprehensive study to date is that of Xie and Chen (2025), who, employing multilevel mixed-effects logistic models with firm-level data from over 1,200 large firms in 48 countries, shows that participation in VCMs is shaped by governance structures, sectoral dynamics, and external pressures. The study finds that firms with stronger Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) structures and commitments to the Sustainable Development Goals are more likely to engage in VCMs, while sectoral heterogeneity plays a decisive role: financial firms respond to compensation incentives and NGO pressure, consumer-facing firms remain less active, and energy firms show weaker engagement when voluntary and compliance markets overlap. Importantly, Xie and Chen (2025) also highlight the lack of research on SMEs as a major gap. In contrast to the weaker engagement of large energy firms, Engler et al. (2023), drawing on survey data from 577 German SMEs, finds that smaller firms often view offsetting as a complement to internal emission reduction strategies, particularly among those covered by the European Union (EU) ETS.

Few studies provide direct evidence on firms' preferences for FCOs. Triana and Ota (2024), using a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) with 58 Japanese SMEs, show that even small firms value non-price attributes, expressing willingness to pay premiums for local forest projects and those delivering employment or biodiversity benefits. In Spain, Morales and Ovando (2025) surveyed 249 organisations enrolled in the national Registry, combining the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) with a DCE. The results showed that social pressures and internal attitudes are strong predictors of offsetting, with organisations displaying a marked preference for domestic projects involving native forest species. These contributions, including the present study, remain rare within the literature, highlighting the scarcity of direct surveys on organisational motivations and preferences for FCOs.

While offering valuable insights, the study by Morales and Ovando (2025) is limited to firms already engaged in voluntary climate impact disclosure mechanisms in Spain, which constrains the broader applicability of its findings. Building on this work, the present study extends the analysis beyond Registry participants by surveying a representative sample of Spanish non-registered firms, allowing direct comparison between organisations engaged in a climate disclosure mechanism and those without any formal engagement. By analysing both groups, the study identifies the main factors shaping offsetting intentions and preferences, providing a more comprehensive view of how Spanish organisations approach the voluntary offsetting of their carbon footprints through forest-based CO₂ removal projects. In addition, it examines whether offsetting behaviour varies systematically across firm sizes and sectors, an issue emphasised in the international literature (e.g., Xie and Chen, 2025; Engler et al., 2023) but not yet addressed in the Spanish context.

Participation in the Registry entails formal engagement with a public carbon accounting and disclosure framework, which may expose firms to different informational requirements, reputational considerations, and organisational learning processes compared to firms operating outside it. Previous research suggests that such institutional engaging is associated with differences in environmental awareness, internal governance structures, and motivations for engaging in voluntary climate action (Lou et al., 2023; Engler et al., 2023). This provides a theoretical rationale for distinguishing between Registry and non-Registry firms

when analysing organisational motivations and preferences for forest carbon offsets.

Crucially, organisational motivations may shape not only the decision to offset, but also how firms evaluate the attributes of forest carbon projects. Evidence from voluntary carbon markets shows that firms driven by reputational concerns, corporate values, or market competitiveness systematically prioritise project characteristics that signal credibility and co-benefits, even at higher costs, whereas firms motivated primarily by cost-efficient carbon management favour cheaper project types (Lou et al., 2023). These behavioural drivers provide a plausible mechanism to influence offsetting preferences regarding project characteristics. While existing studies document heterogeneity in firms' valuation of non-price attributes (Triana and Ota, 2024; Morales and Ovando, 2025), there is still no empirical evidence directly linking attitudinal and organisational characteristics to attribute-specific preferences or to willingness-to-pay estimates derived from stated-preference methods.

The overarching objective is therefore to advance understanding of the drivers and motivations underlying corporate engagement in forest carbon offsetting in Spain. This objective is pursued through three specific research questions:

- Q1:** What economic and non-economic factors influence firms' decisions to engage in forest carbon offsetting?
- Q2:** To what extent do these motivations differ between firms enrolled in the Registry and those outside it?
- Q3:** How are organisational motivations associated with firms' willingness to pay for specific attributes of forest carbon offset projects?

By addressing these questions, the study contributes to the limited but expanding literature on corporate engagement in VCMs, offering novel evidence from Spain. Specifically, it presents the first comparative analysis of firms participating in and beyond a voluntary climate disclosure scheme, advancing understanding of how institutional exposure and organisational motivations shape offsetting preferences and offsetting intentions.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Survey instrument and data collection

The survey instrument combined structured statements derived from the Theory of Planned Behaviour with a Discrete Choice Experiment. Two complementary surveys were implemented: one targeting firms enrolled in the Registry (Survey 1) and another focusing on a representative sample of Spanish non-registered firms (Survey 2). Together, the two surveys provide a basis for comparing firms already engaged in voluntary climate impact disclosure with those that are not.

Both surveys included identical TPB-based statements (section 2.2), measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strong disagreement) to 5 (strong agreement). A shorter scale was selected to minimise respondent burden and improve response rates (Babakus and Mangold, 1992). It should be noted that, for items measuring risk perception, higher scores indicate more negative evaluations (i.e. a stronger perception of risk), as the interpretation of these statements is inverted relative to the other constructs.

The Discrete Choice Experiment (section 2.3) assessed firms' preferences for acquiring FCOs from hypothetical forest carbon removal projects. To ensure accurate carbon unit quantities, organisations were segmented into two groups based on their observed (Survey 1) and expected (Survey 2) GHG emission levels, as described in Section 2.1.2.

2.1.1 Data collection and participants recruitment strategy

Survey 1 relied on a subsample of [Morales and Ovando \(2025\)](#), restricting the analysis to private firms only ($N_1 = 213$). The survey was conducted online between November 2023 and March 2024, targeting decision-makers responsible for social responsibility and/or sustainability practices in Spanish organisations that had recorded their carbon footprint in the Registry at least once before November 2023. As a result, all participants were already familiar with the Registry and its terminology.

Organisations were contacted using publicly available information on their websites. Initial contact was made by telephone to identify the appropriate respondent and to send the survey link to the person in charge of social responsibility or sustainability within the organization. To ensure anonymity, unique alphanumeric codes were generated for each organisation, allowing survey responses to be matched with publicly available organisational data while preserving confidentiality. Through this approach, additional firm-level information—including carbon footprint, sector, organization size category, and carbon offset acquisitions—was retrieved from the Registry.

Survey 2 was administered by an external firm specialising in professional survey implementation between April and May 2024. To avoid the over-representation of micro-firms (which account for approximately 60% of all active firms in Spain ([INE, 2023](#))), the target population was restricted to firms with at least three employees listed in the Iberian Balance Sheet Analysis System (SABI) database. From a pool of 20,000 eligible firms randomly selected using SABI's sampling mechanism, potential respondents were first contacted by telephone and subsequently invited to participate via email, using the contact information provided by the firms.

To ensure confidentiality, the survey company anonymised all firm-level information throughout the data collection process. The resulting dataset identifies participating firms only through anonymised codes indicating sector of activity and firm size, without revealing the identity of individual firms. Consequently, the authors were unable to identify which specific firms responded, while retaining access to their key structural characteristics.

The Survey 2 questionnaire included items on firm size (categorised by number of employees and annual turnover) and sector or industry, allowing the construction of categorical variables directly comparable to those used in Survey 1.

The target was to obtain a minimum of 300 valid responses, with quotas set by industry sector to ensure representativeness of Spanish firms with more than three employees: industry (12%), construction (12%), commerce (22%), and services (54%). Quotas were also aligned with the size distribution of active firms in Spain as of 1 January 2023 ([INE, 2023](#)): 52% with 3–5 employees, 22% with 6–9 employees, 14% with 10–19 employees, and 12% with 20 or more employees².

Both surveys and their data collection strategies were favourably evaluated by the Ethics Committee of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) (References: 242/2023 and 72/2024, respectively).

2.1.2 Segmentation strategies

For Survey 1, the segmentation was determined using the median annual equivalent carbon dioxide emissions (t CO₂e) of organisations in the Registry (115.58 t CO₂e year⁻¹) as the reference point, classifying them as low emitters (Segment A) and high emitters (Segment B). Segment A has a median emission level of 23.31 t CO₂e year⁻¹, Segment B has a median emission of 821.81 t CO₂e year⁻¹.

²Firm distribution statistics correspond to 2023, as these were the most recent figures available at the time the survey was conducted.

For Survey 2, the segmentation strategy was based on organisational size. Because 90 % of firms classified as “Large Enterprises” in the Registry (i.e., those with more than 250 employees) fell within Segment B (high emitters), organisational size provided a highly reliable proxy for emission intensity. Accordingly, non-registered firms were assigned to Segment A or B using this criterion: enterprises with more than 250 employees were classified as high emitters (Segment B), while smaller firms were categorised as low emitters (Segment A).

Offsetting options were presented in units of 10 t CO₂ for Segment A and 100 t CO₂ for Segment B. Using these quantities facilitated the estimation of total costs for the hypothetical carbon offset projects.

2.2 The Theory of Planned Behaviour

2.2.1 Framework and Hypotheses

Behavioural economics uses variants of traditional economic assumptions, often grounded in psychological insights, to explain and predict decision-making, extending the scope of standard economic analysis (Laibson and List, 2015). In business contexts, it examines how cognitive limitations, biases, and non-economic motivations influence organisational choices (Monahan, 2018). This perspective aligns with evidence that business decisions, such as investment or entrepreneurial entry, are not determined solely by financial considerations but are also shaped by behavioural constructs, including individual dispositions, social expectations, and perceived capacity to act, as demonstrated in applications of the Theory of Planned Behaviour to investment decisions (East, 1993) and entrepreneurship (Kautonen et al., 2013).

Within this line of research, the TPB (Ajzen, 1991) is a widely used framework for predicting behaviour through intention-related factors and has been extensively applied to environmental decision-making (Daddi et al., 2018; Yuriev et al., 2020; Wani et al., 2025). According to Ajzen (1991), behaviour is determined by three components: attitudes, defined as the individual’s overall evaluation of expected outcomes, shaped by the strength of convictions and subjective assessments of consequences; subjective norms, which capture the perceived social pressure from relevant actors to engage in—or abstain from—that behaviour (Yeh et al., 2021); and perceived behavioural control, which reflects the perceived ease or difficulty of undertaking the behaviour, depending on available resources and opportunities (Ajzen, 1991).

The TPB framework also permits the inclusion of additional predictors (Ajzen, 1991). In this study, perceived risk is incorporated, defined as the subjective evaluation of the probability and severity of adverse events (Slovic, 1987). This construct is particularly relevant in voluntary forest carbon markets, where projects are exposed to natural and human-induced disturbances that may compromise stored carbon, raise greenwashing concerns, and undermine the credibility of issued credits (Shashi et al., 2023).

The TPB constructs were measured through a set of structured Likert-scale statements, as described in Section 2.1. These items were either adapted from established sources or developed specifically for this study, drawing on insights from in-depth interviews with stakeholders engaged in the Registry (see Table A1 in the Appendix). Attitudes (ATT) reflect the extent to which organisations associate offsetting with positive outcomes, such as enhancing corporate visibility, strengthening internal cohesion, generating rural employment, and contributing to biodiversity conservation. Subjective Norms (SN) denote the perceived expectations of clients and partners and/or shareholders, as well as the influence of peer firms operating in the same industry or sector. Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) refers to organisations’ assessment of their financial resources, access to information, and autonomy in decision-making regarding offsetting. Finally, Perceived

Risk (RSK) addresses concerns about the reliability and permanence of offsets, including risks of greenwashing or project failure.

In both surveys, the effect of the TPB constructs was measured directly on offsetting intention (*Offset*). The Behaviour (BEH) construct is represented by two dummies. Offsetting intention was operationalised through the variable *PastOffsets*, coded 1 if the firm had already offset its carbon footprint and 0 otherwise. In Survey 1 (Registry firms), *PastOffsets* was constructed by triangulating Registry records with survey responses, including offsets both within and outside Spain. In Survey 2 (outside the Registry), the same variable was derived from self-reported answers to the offsetting items.

Survey 2 also included an additional measure of *Awareness*, coded 1 if the firm reported knowledge of the Registry and 0 otherwise. This variable was excluded from Survey 1, as all respondents were necessarily aware of the Registry by virtue of their participation. In both surveys, firms were also asked about their *DeclaredIntention* to offset in the future, coded 1 if they reported such an intention and 0 otherwise, serving as a complementary indicator of behavioural propensity.

Taken together, *PastOffsets*, *DeclaredIntention*, and (for Survey 2) *Awareness* were used to estimate *Offset*, which is treated as the dependent variable in our TPB analysis, as explained in section 2.2.2.

Building on these constructs, and considering firms' offsetting intention as a proxy for decision-makers' behaviour, the following hypotheses are formulated to address the first and second research questions:

- H1:** Attitudes have a positive effect on offsetting behaviour in voluntary forest carbon markets.
- H2:** Offsetting behaviour is influenced by subjective norms, including client and partners and/or shareholder opinions as well as peer firm actions.
- H3:** Perceived behavioural control has a positive effect on the decision to offset emissions.
- H4:** Perceived risk negatively influences the decision to participate in voluntary carbon markets.
- H5:** Perceived risk negatively affects perceived behavioural control.
- H6:** Attitudes positively affect perceived behavioural control.

2.2.2 Structural equation modelling

A Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach was employed to analyse the relationships between the TPB constructs and the additional predictors (ATT, SN, PBC, and RSK) in relation to offsetting behaviour. PLS-SEM is a variance-based technique widely applied in TPB research, particularly suitable for exploratory studies and for data derived from Likert-scale responses

Following the recommended two-step procedure (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988), the measurement model was first assessed to evaluate indicator reliability, internal consistency, and convergent and discriminant validity. Subsequently, the structural model was tested to examine the hypothesised relationships among constructs, taking into account the explanatory power of R^2 values (Cohen, 2022). Bootstrapping with 10,000 resamples was applied to evaluate the robustness and significance of the path coefficients, thereby avoiding reliance on assumptions of data normality (Hair et al., 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2021).

In evaluating the measurement model, Cronbach's alpha, Dillon-Goldstein's rho, and Composite Reliability (CR) were examined, with values above 0.70 indicating acceptable

reliability (Nunnally, 1967). Convergent validity was assessed through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), while discriminant validity was evaluated using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and the Fornell–Larcker criterion (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), requiring AVE values above 0.50 and inter-construct correlations below the square root of the corresponding AVE. Latent construct scores were subsequently extracted and incorporated into logistic models, as described next.

2.3 Discrete Choice Experiment

The discrete choice experiment builds on Morales and Ovando (2025), extending the firm sample to provide a more comprehensive overview of the neutrality strategies adopted by Spanish firms. The design follows a full-factorial structure, retaining the four key attributes and the binary response format to evaluate the acceptability of forest-based carbon removal projects and firms’ willingness to pay for specific project characteristics (Table 1).

Table 1: Attributes and levels of the Discrete Choice Experiment

Attribute	Levels	Quantity
Project type	Forest creation	1
	Forest restoration	-1
Tree species	Native	1
	Non-native	-1
Location	Within Spain	1
	Abroad	-1
Price per t CO ₂	€5; €20 €50; €100	Price is continuous

The experimental design includes an opt–out alternative (“reject project”), which ensures a consistent valuation and allows firms to express a meaningful preference for non-participation (Hoyos, 2010). Attributes represent the types of projects listed in the Registry, particularly forest creation and restoration, and vary in tree species (slow-growing native vs. fast-growing non-native), geographic location (domestic vs. international), and price levels informed by stakeholders.

2.3.1 Econometric models

To analyse the DCE, we adopt the random utility framework (McFadden, 1974). A standard multinomial logit (MNL) model is estimated as a baseline to assess internal consistency and model fit, but given its restrictive substitution patterns and limited capacity to capture heterogeneity, its results are reported only in the Appendix. The core empirical analysis instead relies on two complementary specifications: a mixed logit (MXL) model, which accommodates continuous variation in preferences across firms, and a Willingness to Pay.

The goal of the empirical analysis is twofold. First, we seek to quantify how firms value key project attributes³, and whether these preferences vary systematically with psychological constructs or firm characteristics. Second, we aim to determine whether these influences operate smoothly across the population or whether they instead delineate distinct behavioural regimes among firms.

³All attributes in the DCE were effects–coded, following best practice in stated choice analysis (Bech and Gyrd-Hansen, 2005; Hensher et al., 2015).

2.3.2 Mixed logit model

The mixed logit model generalises the standard logit by allowing taste parameters to vary between firms, providing a flexible representation of continuous heterogeneity (McFadden and Train, 2000; Train, 2009). To account for firm-level heterogeneity, we specify the alternative specific constant (ASC) as a function of time-invariant firm characteristics and TPB constructs. Since project attributes vary across choice tasks while firm characteristics remain constant across the eight choice cards presented to each respondent, these variables enter the model through the ASC rather than as attribute interactions (Hensher et al., 2015). This specification allows us to test whether behavioural predispositions systematically affect baseline acceptance of offsetting projects.

The random utility difference for firm n and task t is:

$$U_{nt} = \beta'_n x_{nt} + \epsilon_{nt}, \quad (1)$$

where β_n is a vector of firm-specific random coefficients drawn from a parametric distribution. In our specification, the coefficients for project type and location and the alternative-specific constant for accepting the project (ASC_{accept}) are normally distributed, while the species coefficient follows a triangular distribution reflecting monotonic preferences. The price coefficient is kept fixed to facilitate welfare analysis.

Conditional on β_n , the probability of accepting the project is:

$$L_{nt}(\beta_n) = \frac{\exp((\beta_n x_{nt}))}{1 + \exp(\beta_n x_{nt})}. \quad (2)$$

The unconditional choice probability integrates over the distribution of β :

$$P(y_{nt} = 1) = \int L_{nj}(\beta) f(\beta | \theta) d\beta, \quad (3)$$

where $f(\beta | \theta)$ denotes the mixing distribution. Since this integral has no closed form, the model is estimated using simulated maximum likelihood using Halton sequences (Train, 2003). To ensure stable inference, we adopt a simulation-based convergence procedure: the number of draws is iteratively increased until successive estimates satisfy pre-defined tolerances for changes in coefficients, standard errors and log-likelihood.

The mixed logit model thus provides the main welfare results and captures the continuous dispersion of preferences, including how this dispersion correlates with constructs such as Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control and Risk.

2.3.3 Willingness to pay

Because the mixed logit framework recovers both mean preferences and their underlying heterogeneity, it also forms the basis for deriving welfare-consistent measures of willingness to pay (WTP). Within the random utility model, the WTP associated with attribute k is defined as the marginal rate of substitution between that attribute and the cost attribute:

$$WTP_k = -\frac{\beta_k}{\beta_p}. \quad (4)$$

To assess the statistical precision of these monetary valuations, we compute WTP using two complementary procedures. First, the Delta method provides asymptotic standard errors by approximating the variance of the ratio of coefficients. Second, Krinsky–Robb

simulations (Krinsky and Robb, 1986) generate empirical confidence intervals through repeated draws from the estimated variance–covariance matrix. This combined approach ensures that the resulting WTP estimates reflect both parameter uncertainty and the heterogeneity captured by the mixed logit specification.

2.3.4 DCE Experimental hypotheses

By modelling project choices through conditional and mixed logit specifications, the DCE enables the analysis of how economic and non-economic attributes shape offsetting decisions, while accounting for systematic differences between registered and non-registered firms. This framework provides the foundation for testing whether project characteristics and firm-level heterogeneity are reflected in observable differences in offset preferences and willingness to pay. On this basis, the following hypotheses were advanced:

- H7:** Firms will show a higher preference for national projects rather than abroad.
- H8:** Firms will prefer offsetting projects involving native species over those involving non-native species.
- H9:** There are significant differences in the willingness to pay of Registry and non-registered firms.

2.3.5 Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney U Test

The Wilcoxon-Mann–Whitney (WMW) U or rank-sum test is a non-parametric statistical test designed to assess whether two independent samples are drawn from the same distribution (Mann and Whitney, 1947; Nachar et al., 2008). Unlike parametric alternatives such as the Student’s t-test, this method does not require the assumption of normality and is therefore suitable for small samples, ordinal data, and non-symmetric distributions. Its null hypothesis (H_0) states that the two groups are stochastically equal, i.e. that the distributions of the two groups do not differ systematically. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) posits a difference in central tendency between the groups.

Formally, let n_x and n_y denote the number of observations in groups X and Y , respectively, and R_x the sum of ranks assigned to the observations of group X . The Mann–Whitney statistics are defined as:

$$U_x = n_x n_y + \frac{n_x(n_x + 1)}{2} - R_x, \quad (5)$$

$$U_y = n_x n_y + \frac{n_y(n_y + 1)}{2} - R_y, \quad (6)$$

with R_y being the sum of ranks for group Y . The test statistic is then:

$$U = \min(U_x, U_y). \quad (7)$$

Intuitively, U represents the number of times observations in one sample precede those in the other when all observations are ranked jointly. In the case of ties, average ranks are assigned.

The hypotheses tested are:

- H_0 : The two groups are stochastically equal (no systematic difference in central tendency).
- H_1 : The two groups differ in central tendency.

The WMW test was applied to compare responses across firm groups when Likert-scale data were used. This non-parametric approach, appropriate for ordinal data and free from distributional assumptions, ensures robust inference on group differences. Comparisons were made not only between registered and non-registered firms, but also across other characteristics, including respondent gender and firm size, and, in Survey 2, whether firms reported awareness of the Registry.

3 Results

A total of 1,634 organizations participated in the surveys, yielding 522 valid responses (32%) retained for analysis ($N_1 = 213$ firms in the Registry, $N_2 = 309$ outside the Registry). Only fully completed questionnaires were included. The samples can be considered representative of their respective target populations, as the characteristics of the responding firms align closely with the distribution of firms by sector and size.

Table 2 shows that the two samples differ significantly from each other (Z-test, $p < 0.05$). Key differences concern firm size, with non-registered firms comprising predominantly small and medium-sized firms, whereas firms in the Registry are more likely to have dedicated sustainability departments and a higher proportion of women respondents.

The surveys also successfully reached individuals within firms who hold decision-making responsibilities for environmental and climate-related actions. In the Registry sample, Most respondents were either sustainability managers (51.17%) or CEOs (20.8%). In the sample outside the Registry, respondents were mainly CEOs (40.01%) or individuals responsible for finance or administration (30.46%), ensuring that responses reflected the views of those with relevant managerial authority.

Table 2: Respondents characteristics by sample

Respondents characteristics	Registry [N = 213]	Non-Registry [N = 309]
Production Sector		
Agriculture	3,75%	3.88%
Industry	12,21%	12.62%
Construction***	32,39%	11.33%
Services***	51,64%	47.57%
Trade***	–	24.60%
Firm Size		
Micro***	26,29%	62.25%
Medium/Big***	43,66%	26.16%
Small***	30,05%	11.59%
Position		
CEO***	21,43%	40,01%
Financial / Admin. Dept.***	8,45%	30,46%
Marketing	3,76%	1,99%
Social Responsibility	3,76%	1,99%
Sustainability***	51,17%	10,93%
Other Department (Quality, Technical, ...)***	11,74%	5,63%
Gender		
Woman***	47,89%	38,74%
Men***	50,7%	59,93%
N/A	1,41%	1,32%
Awareness of the registry existence	–	48.22%
Intention to offset in the future	43.19%	9.39%

***Statistical difference between samples (Z-test, $p < 0.05$)

3.1 Organisational Context and Awareness in TPB Responses

The two surveys provide complementary insights into how Spanish firms perceive and engage with forest carbon offsetting in the context of the Theory of Planned Behaviour. Overall, both groups show the highest levels of agreement with statements reflecting positive attitudes toward offsetting. These include the visibility of climate actions (ATT1), and rural employment opportunities (ATT2). However, the degree of endorsement differs: firms in the Registry consistently report stronger agreement, while non-registered firms rely more heavily on neutral responses, frequently selecting the midpoint of the 5-point Likert scale (see S.1 in supplementary material).

Similarities are observed across both samples regarding the perceived reputational benefits of offsetting. Items such as ATT3 (improves corporate image) and ATT4 (generates market opportunities for environmental services) receive relatively high levels of agreement in both surveys, indicating that reputation and positioning are widely recognised drivers.

Differences are most evident in perceived behavioural control (PBC). Registry firms report greater confidence in their economic and technological capacities to achieve net-zero before 2050 (PBC4), as well as in the potential of carbon offsetting to reduce the costs of reaching this goal (PBC1). Nonetheless, some scepticism persists regarding its essential role in achieving neutrality (PBC2). In contrast, non-registered firms more often provide neutral or negative responses, particularly concerning their resources and information to offset emissions (PBC3) and their overall ability to achieve neutrality. These patterns indicate a weaker perception of internal capacity among firms not engaged in the Registry, also suggesting that direct involvement in climate disclosure mechanisms is associated with stronger and more consistent perceptions of capacity to undertake offsetting.

Perceptions of risk also diverge. Registry firms are more likely to recognise potential reputational challenges, such as the risk of offsetting being perceived as greenwashing (RSK3). In contrast, non-registered firms are more neutral, possibly reflecting limited familiarity with the debates surrounding carbon market integrity. This neutrality extends to subjective norms, as non-registered firms are less likely to perceive strong client (SN1), partners and/or shareholders (SN2), or competitor (SN3) expectations or valuation for undertaken offsetting.

The differences in responses to TPB statements between registered and non-registered firms, as well as gender-related differences and variation among non-registered firms depending on their awareness of the Registry, are presented in Table 3, based on the WMW-test. The table indicates whether statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) exist between groups and, where they do, the direction of these differences (increasing or decreasing agreement with TPB statements).

For most TPB statements (73%), non-registered firms report significantly lower levels of agreement compared with firms inside, which are taken as the reference group. Significant differences are observed for items relating to visibility of climate efforts (ATT1), corporate image (ATT3), environmental-related market opportunities (ATT4), cost reduction in net-zero efforts (PBC1), sufficient resources for offsetting (PBC3), and technological capacities for achieving net-zero (PBC4), and several risk and subjective norm items (RSK2, RSK3, RSK4, SN1, SN2). These results indicate that Registry firms express stronger confidence in the role of offsetting for achieving net-zero and are also more aware of associated risks. They further perceive greater value attached to offsetting by clients and partners and/or shareholders. By contrast, no significant differences are found for rural employment creation (ATT2), the essential role of offsetting in achieving neutrality (PBC2), risk of fires or climate change (RSK1), and competitor engagement (SN3). The absence of differences in these items suggests areas where Registry participation does not strongly influence firms' views. Interestingly, while non-registered firms do not express stronger agreement overall,

Registry firms appear more likely to connect offsetting with broader climate neutrality (net-zero efforts) efforts and stakeholder expectations, consistent with their role as early adopters in climate disclosure and offsetting mechanisms.

Table 3: Differences in responses distribution based on the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test*

Code	Statement	Registry (1 Yes 1 (vs. 2 No) N= 522 [‡]	Awareness (1 Yes) (vs. 2 No) N= 309 [‡]
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm’s net-zero efforts.	↓	↔
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	↔	↓
ATT3	Improves firms’s corporate image.	↓	↓
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	↓	↓
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	↓	↔
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm’s net-zero goal.	↔	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	↓	↓
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	↓	↓
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	↔	↔
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	↓	↔
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	↓	↔
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	↓	↔
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	↑	↓
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	↓	↓
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	↔	↓

Notes:

* Arrows show changes of category 2 (comparison group) with respect to category 1 (reference group), indicating: ↔, No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑ Significant differences increasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓ Significant differences decreasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$).

[‡] Includes firms both inside (213) and outside (309) the Registry.

[‡] Includes only non-registered firms that were aware (149) or not aware (160) of this disclosure mechanism.

Within the group of non-registered firms, awareness of this climate disclosure mechanism is associated with systematic differences in several TPB statements. Firms that are aware of the Registry are more likely to report that clients and partners and/or shareholders value offsetting and that competitors are also undertaking offsetting actions (SN1–SN3). They also express stronger positive attitudes towards offsetting, including its contribution to rural employment (ATT2), corporate image (ATT3), and market opportunities for environmental services (ATT4). Notably, no significant differences are observed between firms aware and unaware of the Registry with respect to offsetting’s role in enhancing the visibility of net-zero efforts (ATT1), its perceived effect on reducing costs (PBC1), its necessity for achieving neutrality (PBC2), or any of the risk-related items (RSK1–RSK4). The fact that perceptions of risk do not differ suggests that awareness of the Registry

primarily shapes views of external expectations and reputational or market benefits, rather than concerns about offsetting-related risks. These findings show a consistent pattern, as both Registry participation and awareness of the Registry are associated with stronger positive attitudes and clearer perceptions of external expectations.

3.2 Differences in behavioural constructs towards forest carbon offsets

3.2.1 Measurement model

The measurement models were estimated separately for registered and non-registered firms to ensure sample adequacy. Variable selection in each specification was guided by the indicators' factor loadings, and constructs were retained only once they satisfied the required criteria for internal consistency and discriminant validity. A complete description of the TPB constructs, indicator performance, and the final measurement model specifications is provided in Appendix A.2.

In both models, Table 4 show factor loadings above 0.70, indicating that each variable loads strongly on its intended construct and supporting item reliability. Composite Reliability and Dillon–Goldstein's rho (ρ) values consistently exceed the benchmark of 0.70, confirming internal consistency across constructs. Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values meet or surpass the minimum criterion of 0.50, demonstrating that the constructs in both models adequately capture the variance explained by their indicators.

To evaluate discriminant validity, the Fornell–Larcker criterion was applied (see Table A6 in the Appendix). According to this criterion, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct should be greater than its correlations with any other construct. This requirement is met in both models, as the values on the main diagonal of the matrix (representing the square root of the AVE) consistently exceed the corresponding inter-construct correlations, thereby confirming discriminant validity.

3.2.2 Structural model and testing RHC's TPB constructs

Following the validation of the measurement model, the structural model was estimated using bootstrap re-sampling to evaluate the hypothesised relationships. The results indicate differences between registered and non-registered firms in the main predictors of offsetting behaviour (Table 5).

Among Registry firms, behaviour is primarily driven by *attitudes* ($\beta = 0.296$), with *subjective norms* exerting a significant influence ($\beta = 0.167$). The analysis also confirms an indirect effect of risk on behaviour through PBC, suggesting that risk does affect the behaviour by diminishing the perception of control. For non-registered firms, the strongest predictor of behaviour is *perceived behavioural control* ($\beta = 0.203$), followed by subjective norms ($\beta = 0.127$). In this group, attitudes exhibit only a weak and non-significant direct effect on behaviour.

Overall, the structural model exhibits substantially greater explanatory power for Registry firms ($R_{\text{BEH}}^2 = 0.20$) than for non-registered firms ($R_{\text{BEH}}^2 = 0.09$), indicating that TPB constructs, particularly attitudes and subjective norms, are more predictive of behavioural intentions within the Registry context. This pattern is consistent with the corresponding goodness-of-fit indices (0.24 for Registry firms and 0.19 for non-Registry firms), which confirm that the model fits the data adequately in both sub-samples while providing a noticeably better account of behavioural variance among Registry participants.

Table 4: Variables, factor loading's and models fit indicators'.

Constructs' variables and statements α^a : (Inside/Outside the Registry)		Registry				Non-Registry			
		Loading ^b	CR ^c	Rho(ρ) ^d	AVE ^e	Loading ^b	CR ^c	Rho(ρ) ^d	AVE ^e
<i>Attitudes: $\alpha^I = 0.73 / \alpha^O = 0.801$</i>									
ATT1	Visibility of firm's net-zero efforts	0.841	0.941	0.850	0.643	0.858	0.967	0.883	0.714
ATT2	Rural employment generation	0.768				0.855			
ATT3	Improves corporate image	-				-			
ATT4	Market opportunities	0.797				0.822			
<i>Subjective Norms: $\alpha^I = 0.75 / \alpha^O = 0.795$</i>									
SN1	Our clients value it	0.700	0.949	0.856	0.665	0.917	0.957	0.880	0.706
SN2	Our partners/shareholders value it	0.718				0.856			
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset carbon footprint	0.951				0.738			
<i>Perceived B. Control: $\alpha^I = 0.70 / \alpha^O = 0.824$</i>									
PBC1	Reduce cost for achieving net-zero	-	0.970	0.868	0.755	-	0.987	0.919	0.835
PBC2	Essential for achieving net-zero	-				-			
PBC3	Sufficient resources and information for offsetting	0.939				0.969			
PBC4	Economic and/or technological capacity for net-zero	0.793				0.856			
<i>Risk: $\alpha^I = 0.71 / \alpha^O = 0.778$</i>									
RSK1	Risky investment (fires)	-	0.926	0.840	0.615	-	0.940	0.871	0.664
RSK2	Not a real GHG reduction	0.806				0.917			
RSK3	Green-washing risks	0.820				0.842			
RSK4	Divert resources to reduce GHG	0.724				0.687			
<i>Behaviour: $\alpha^I = 0.51 / \alpha^O = 0.334$</i>									
Declared Intention	Plans to offset in the future 1= YES; 0=NO	0.812	0.954	0.803	0.671	0.846	0.909	0.750	0.597
Past Offsets	Has offset in the past? 1= YES; 0=NO	0.826				-			
Awareness	of the Registry's existence	-				0.691			

Notes:

^a Cronbach's alpha (α^I for Registry firms and α^O for Non-Registry firms), with $\alpha > 0.70$ for a very good fit; ^b Loading's > 0.70 for a very good fit; ^c Dillon-Goldstein's rho > 0.70 for a very good fit; ^d Composite reliability > 0.70 for a very good fit; ^e Average Variance Extracted > 0.50 for a very good fit

Table 5: Hypothesis testing by Bootstrap re-sample results.

Hypotheses	Path	Registry		Non-Registry	
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta	Std. Error
H1+	ATT → BEH	0.296***	0.064	0.058	0.055
H2+	SN → BEH	0.167***	0.065	0.127***	0.054
H3+	PBC → BEH	0.123***	0.057	0.203***	0.060
H4 -	RSK → BEH	-0.073	0.074	0.014	0.071
H5 -	RSK → ATT	-0.145	0.082	-0.255***	0.065
H6 -	RSK → PBC	-0.189***	0.081	0.033	0.071

To integrate behavioural constructs from the TPB framework into the choice models, we extracted latent variable scores from the validated structural models for each respondent. These scores represent weighted composites of the indicators for Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control, and Risk, standardized to facilitate interpretation. The latent scores were then merged with the choice experiment data and incorporated as covariates in the alternative-specific constant of the mixed logit models, allowing us to test whether psychological predispositions systematically influence project acceptance beyond the effect of observed attributes.

3.3 Differences in preferences towards forest carbon projects

3.3.1 Differences in the forestry projects characteristics affecting offsetting decisions [Q2]

Table 6 reports the mixed logit estimates for registered and non-registered firms. The models' results confirm that Registry participants display more structured preferences for project attributes than non-participants. For registered firms, the coefficients for Species and Location are positive and highly significant, while Project type remains non-significant. This indicates a clear preference for projects using native species and implemented within Spain. The price coefficient is negative and precisely estimated, implying a substantial decrease in the probability of project acceptance as the cost per tCO₂ increases.

By contrast, non-registered firms only exhibit a statistically significant preference for domestic location, whereas species and project type do not systematically affect their choices. Price sensitivity is again strong and negative, but smaller in magnitude than for Registry firms. Together, these patterns suggest that firms already engaged with the Registry are both more responsive to quality attributes and more willing to discriminate between project configurations, while non-participants react mainly to whether the project is located in Spain.

The large and significant standard deviations of the ASC (2.658 for Registry, 4.805 for Non-Registry) reveal substantial unobserved heterogeneity in firms' baseline propensity to accept offsetting projects. This finding underscores the importance of accounting for random preferences in choice models, as firms' acceptance decisions are influenced by factors beyond the observed project attributes and firm characteristics included in our model.

To formally assess whether the two groups differ in their preferences beyond simple coefficient-by-coefficient comparisons, we conducted a Swait–Louviere test. The optimal scale factor for non-Registry firms is $\hat{\mu} = 0.46$, indicating considerably higher decision noise relative to Registry firms. The hypothesis of equal preferences up to this scale adjustment is decisively rejected ($LR = 35.93$, $df = 5$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that Registry participation is associated not only with lower error variance but also with genuinely different preference structures.

Table 6: Mixed logit models (Registry and Non-Registry firms)

Variable	Mixed logit	
	Registry	Non-Registry
Project	-0.001 (0.075)	0.133 (0.092)
Specie	0.239*** (0.076)	0.115 (0.091)
Location	0.439*** (0.087)	0.250*** (0.096)
Price	-0.037*** (0.003)	-0.027*** (0.003)
ASC_accept	0.727** (0.355)	-1.059 (0.955)
Attitudes	0.560** (0.221)	0.428 (0.415)
PBC	0.292 (0.218)	0.974** (0.380)
Subjective Norms	0.349 (0.226)	0.688* (0.409)
Risk	-0.094 (0.213)	0.143 (0.346)
<i>Service Sector</i> ^a	1.020** (0.420)	-0.944 (0.582)
<i>< 50 Employees</i> ^b	-0.445 (0.412)	-2.468** (0.979)
Random parameters (std. dev.)		
sd(Project)	0.006 (0.174)	0.005 (0.182)
sd(Specie)	0.150 (0.345)	0.001 (0.166)
sd(Location)	0.493*** (0.153)	0.279 (0.259)
sd(ASC_accept)	2.658*** (0.247)	4.805*** (0.496)
Goodness of fit		
Log-likelihood	-638.41	-799.32
AIC	1306.82	1628.63
Pseudo R^2	0.458	0.316
Valid Choices	1704	2472
Observations	213	309
Halton Draws	1300	700

Notes: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors in parentheses.

Price refers to the difference in the cost attribute between the project alternative and the status quo. Project, Specie and Location are effects-coded differences between the project and the opt-out alternative.

^a Dummy = 1 if the firm's main economic activity is in the service sector.

^b Dummy = 1 if the firm has fewer than 50 employees (micro to small firms).

3.3.2 Differences in the willingness to pay for carbon units and project attributes (Q3)

To obtain consistent and comparable willingness-to-pay estimates, we re-estimated a set of mixed logit models using only low-emitting firms in both samples. Because the Spanish sample is composed almost entirely of Segment A organisations, who faced a contribution for 10 tonnes, we similarly restricted the Registry sample to Segment A firms. This avoids introducing artificial heterogeneity from Segment B organisations in the Registry group and ensures that differences in WTP reflect substantive preference variation rather than structural differences in baseline emissions or contribution size. The full estimation results for these mixed logit models are reported in the Appendix A6.

Table 7 summarises the resulting marginal WTP values for each attribute and the total WTP for a representative afforestation project. The contrast between the two groups is substantial. Among Registry participants, total WTP reaches €30.9/tCO₂, driven by strong and statistically robust preferences for native species and projects located within Spain. Both attributes exert significant positive effects on choice probabilities. In contrast,

non-registered firms (Segment A) exhibit a more moderate total WTP of €18.5 tCO₂. In this group, only the domestic location attribute is consistently valued, while preferences for species and project type are weaker and not systematically significant.

Overall, Registry participants display a markedly higher, more structured, and more coherent willingness to pay for high-quality domestic forestry offsets than non-registered firms.

Table 7: Willingness to Pay (WTP) by Sample (Registry vs. Spain, Segment A)

	Registry $N = 69$	Non-Registry $N = 302$
<i>Delta method: WTP (SE)</i>		
Project	3.76* (1.82)	4.89** (1.84)
Specie	12.96*** (1.91)	4.18* (1.83)
Location	14.22*** (2.05)	9.46*** (1.90)
TOTAL	30.94*** (2.59)	18.53*** (2.47)
<i>Krinsky-Robb: WTP [95% CI]</i>		
Project	3.76 [-2.97, 10.49]	4.95 [-1.71, 11.80]
Specie	13.05*** [5.94, 20.74]	4.25 [-2.39, 11.12]
Location	14.31*** [6.13, 23.25]	9.57** [2.52, 17.07]
TOTAL	31.12*** [18.06, 45.37]	18.76** [6.90, 31.51]

Notes: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

4 Discussion

4.1 Behavioural Drivers of Offsetting

As climate regulation intensifies, firms have become key actors in climate mitigation. Beyond compliance-based instruments, voluntary approaches provide a pathway to demonstrate their commitment to net-zero efforts. However, uptake remains low, highlighting the need to understand why only some firms engage in voluntary carbon markets. By comparing firms participating in a national climate disclosure programme with non-participating firms, this study shows how behavioural attitudes, organisational characteristics, awareness of climate disclosure mechanisms, and the integration of sustainability functions within corporate structures influence preferences for forest carbon offsets.

To examine the psychological drivers of offsetting decisions, we estimated two structural models. In both, perceived behavioural control emerged as the strongest determinant of offsetting behaviour. PBC reflects firms' perceptions of having sufficient resources and information to undertake offsetting activities (PBC3), as well as the economic and technological capacities required to progress towards net-zero objectives (PBC4). This result suggests that most firms consider offsetting to be a feasible and manageable action. Under such conditions, the Theory of Planned Behaviour identifies attitudes as the primary determinant of behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

Registered firms display a pronounced attitudinal and reputational orientation, evident in both structural and random utility models. These attitudes are shaped by three factors: enhanced visibility of net-zero efforts (ATT1), perceived contributions to rural employment (ATT2), and anticipated market opportunities (ATT4). The influence of ATT1 and ATT2 aligns with previous findings that firms with stronger ESG reputational exposure tend to engage more actively in voluntary carbon initiatives (Xie and Chen, 2025; Engler et al., 2023; Lou et al., 2023; Triana and Ota, 2024).

Although both samples report high levels of perceived behavioural control, only registered firms combine perceived feasibility with consistently positive attitudes, making attitudes as the strongest predictor of offsetting behaviour (Papagiannakis and Lioukas, 2012). The alignment between attitudes and perceived control delineates the behavioural boundary between firms that engage in offsetting and those that remain disengaged.

Both groups of firms assign high importance to subjective norms. Firms in the Registry are primarily influenced by the actions of other firms (SN3) and partner and/or shareholder opinions (SN2), closely followed by client expectations (SN1). At the economic level, competitive pressures and interdependencies compel shape firms' strategic responses to the actions of competitors (Levy, 2004), which explains the strong effect of SN3. Conversely, non-registered firms are more influenced by clients' opinions (SN1), followed by partners or shareholders (SN2) and competitors' actions (SN3). Nevertheless, subjective norms remain a key determinant for both samples, consistent with studies showing that external pressures are powerful drivers of firms' net-zero strategies (Zhang et al., 2023). This aligns with Xie and Chen (2025) findings that transnational and domestic pressures, including reputational scrutiny, play a decisive role in shaping corporate engagement in voluntary carbon markets.

Regarding perceived risk, registered firms are primarily concerned with reputational exposure associated with greenwashing (RSK3) and scepticism about the genuine mitigation effect of carbon removal projects (RSK2), followed by the concern that offsetting may divert of resources from internal emission reduction efforts (RSK4). Among non-registered firms, perceived risk is less salient overall; however, it exerts a significant negative effect on attitudes towards offsetting, as evidenced by the TPB structural model. This indicates that, for non-registered firms, risk perceptions undermine attitudinal support rather than directly constraining behaviour. By contrast, among registered firms, perceived risk reduces perceived behavioural control, indicating that risk is internalised as a constraint on feasibility rather than as a challenge to the desirability of offsetting.

These findings are consistent with evidence that integrity challenges in voluntary carbon markets amplify reputational concerns, which firms tend to manage strategically rather than avoid altogether, as argued by Xie and Chen (2025). Lou et al. (2023) shows that firms mitigate credibility concerns by favouring high-standard certifications and projects with verified co-benefits, which act as assurance mechanisms. These findings suggest that risk is internalised through the strategic selection of credible offsetting options, rather than deterring engagement. This is also consistent with evidence from discrete choice experiments showing that organisations exhibit a preference for forest carbon offset projects that deliver verified co-benefits—such as employment generation and biodiversity protection—which enhance project legitimacy and reduce perceived reputational risk (Triana and Ota, 2024).

Finally, behavioural outcomes differed across the two samples, reflecting the distinct ways in which behaviour was measured. Among firms in the Registry, the behavioural construct combined past offsetting actions with stated intentions to compensate in the future. In this group, behaviour was primarily explained by previous engagement in offsetting, indicating a form of behavioural path dependency in which past actions reinforce future commitments. By contrast, for non-registered firms, behaviour was captured through awareness of the Registry's existence and intentions to offset in the future. In this case, the strongest predictor was awareness, suggesting that knowledge of institutional mechanisms acts as a prerequisite for the formation of future behavioural intentions. This finding aligns with evidence that awareness and information are key antecedents of environmental action (Bresciani et al., 2022; Engler et al., 2023).

In response to the first research question, hypotheses H1, H2, H3 and H6 were supported for Registry firms, whereas H2, H3 and H5 received support among non-registered firms. Taken together, the results indicate that while perceived control and social norms influence offsetting decisions across both groups, attitudes toward offsetting represent the main point of divergence between samples, and thus the key determinant of voluntary engagement. This pattern is consistent with Xie and Chen (2025)'s multilevel perspective, which highlights how voluntary participation in carbon markets emerges from the inter-

action between internal governance structures, institutional contexts and transnational pressures.

4.2 Preferences for Forest Carbon Offset Projects

The discrete choice experiment revealed clear and consistent differences between registered and non-registered firms. Across both groups, respondents show a marked preference for national projects, confirming that spatial proximity plays a central role in offsetting choices. This pattern aligns with previous findings showing that both organisations and consumers tend to favour domestic projects over those implemented abroad (Triana and Ota, 2024; Merk et al., 2023). Such preference likely relates with greater perception of control, trust, and accountability within the national context (Baranzini et al., 2018). Furthermore, as noted by Cevallos et al. (2019), the development of local and domestic carbon standards in Europe, often under public oversight, contributes to strengthening credibility and buyer confidence by ensuring trustworthy certification processes and alignment with national climate objectives.

Other determinants for offsetting decisions differ between samples. For registered firms, belonging to the service sector increases the utility of choosing an offsetting option. This is consistent with the effect of subjective norms in the structural model, as service firms operate closer to end users and might be more exposed to reputational expectations and stakeholder scrutiny. Prior research shows that firms that provide service activities adopt voluntary climate actions to strengthen legitimacy and respond to external pressures (Andre and Valenciano-Salazar, 2022).

Firm size emerges as a significant determinant of participation in forest carbon offset projects among non-registered firms, as organisations with fewer than 50 employees are significantly less likely to accept offsetting projects. This pattern is consistent with previous findings showing that larger firms are more likely to engage in voluntary carbon offsetting because they hold greater financial and organisational resources, as well as strategic incentives linked to reputation, stakeholder visibility, and corporate sustainability commitments (Yunus et al., 2016; Xie and Chen, 2025).

Given that the Spanish business structure is dominated by micro and small enterprises (INE, 2024), the limited uptake of offsetting initiatives is unsurprising and reflects structural constraints rather than attitudinal resistance, as smaller firms tend less to adopt environmental practices (Tilley, 2000; Gadenne et al., 2009). This pattern also aligns with trends observed in international VCMs, where demand for forest carbon credits is primarily driven by large corporations—particularly those with formal net-zero targets and the institutional capacity to manage the reputational, administrative, and verification requirements associated with offsetting (Xie and Chen, 2025). It is worth noting that the Registry sample contains a higher share of large firms, which may further contribute to the behavioural differences observed between groups given the structural advantages associated with scale, as firm size positively influences offsetting activity.

Beyond project and firm characteristics, the latent TPB constructs also exert a significant influence on choice outcomes in the mixed logit models. Among registered firms, the latent Attitudes construct increases the probability of accepting carbon removal projects as offsetting tool, underlining its central role in driving participation. In contrast, for non-registered firms, choice probabilities were shaped mainly by Subjective Norms and Perceived Behavioural Control, indicating that their acceptance of offsetting options depends more on external expectations and perceived feasibility than on internal attitudes towards offsetting.

The WTP estimates reveal a clear divide between the two groups. Registry firms display a substantially higher and more coherent WTP, driven by strong preferences for native

species and domestic projects—consistent with evidence that organisations pay premiums for high-quality offsets offering local co-benefits (Triana and Ota, 2024) and enhanced reputational value. In contrast, non-registered firms exhibit a more moderate WTP, valuing only domestic location, a pattern aligned with more cost-oriented offsetting behaviour. Overall, Registry participants behave as a climate-engaged segment willing to pay for quality, whereas non-registered firms remain price-sensitive and less responsive to project attributes.

4.3 Future research avenues

Building on these findings, this study opens several avenues for future research to deepen understanding of corporate engagement in voluntary carbon markets. First, while the analysis does not explicitly account for contemporaneous political or regulatory developments, future work could explore how evolving policy frameworks shape firms’ offsetting behaviour and perceptions over time through longitudinal approaches. Second, as the analysis is conducted within the Spanish institutional and regulatory context, the findings provide context-specific insights that invite comparative cross-country studies to assess how different governance structures and voluntary carbon market designs shape organisational motivations and offsetting preferences.

From an analytical perspective, the more modest explanatory power observed in the behavioural model for non-registered firms suggests that additional behavioural or organisational dimensions—such as interactions between mitigation strategies, reputational incentives, and perceptions of project integrity—may further enrich understanding of offsetting decisions among less engaged firms. In addition, the Registry subsample is subject to self-selection, as participating firms are likely to exhibit higher environmental commitment *ex ante*; which is consistent with the comparative design of the study, but calls for cautious when generalising findings to the broader population of Spanish firms. Finally, by focussing on afforestation and forest restoration projects, the discrete choice experiment provides a clear and policy-relevant benchmark, while also highlighting the potential value of extending future stated-preference analyses to alternative offset types, including renewable energy or soil carbon projects, to broaden the empirical basis for policy design.

5 Conclusions

This study provides novel evidence on the factors shaping Spanish firms’ engagement with voluntary forest carbon markets, revealing a clear differentiation between firms participating in formal climate disclosure mechanism and those operating outside such framework. By integrating behavioural and stated preferences approaches, we identify the structural and attitudinal profiles that define offsetting behaviour. Registered firms display stronger pro-offsetting attitudes, greater organisational capacity and a markedly higher willingness to pay for carbon offsets. In contrast, non-registered firms are more likely to reject forest carbon offsetting projects, lack clearly defined attitudes towards carbon offsets, and face size-related constraints that limit their ability to engage.

These findings have direct implications for the design of voluntary climate policy instruments in Spain and the European Union, where voluntary carbon markets are increasingly used to complement regulatory climate action. The Spanish Carbon Footprint Registry constitutes a key institutional tool for mobilising corporate engagement, yet its limited uptake indicates that climate disclosure mechanisms require supportive policy frameworks to become effective at scale.

Encouraging broader participation requires addressing both demand and supply side constraints. On the demand side, economic incentives alone are unlikely to suffice. Policies should instead target organisational attitudes, perceived legitimacy, and behavioural con-

trol, particularly among small and medium enterprises, with measures such as capacity-building initiatives, technical assistance, simplified reporting, and visibility measures, such as public benchmarking or recognition schemes. On the supply side, sustaining voluntary demand depends on the availability of credible, high-quality domestic forest carbon projects. Strong preferences for native species, domestic location, and verified co-benefits point to the need for coordinated public support for project development, expanded eligibility of project types, and robust monitoring and verification frameworks.

Overall, the results indicate that expanding voluntary carbon market participation requires explicit recognition of the heterogeneity incorporate motivations and organisational capacities. Firms participating in the Registry appear both structurally and behaviourally equipped to integrate offsetting into their climate strategies, whereas non-registered firms face informational, and capacity-related constraints that limit engagement. Bridging this divide will require policy interventions tailored to firms' behavioural foundations, alongside sustained efforts to ensure transparency, credibility, and high-quality standards in the provision of forest carbon offsets.

References

- I. Ajzen. The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 1991.
- J. C. Anderson and D. W. Gerbing. structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(3):411—423, 1988. URL <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.103.3.411>.
- F. J. Andre and J. A. Valenciano-Salazar. Voluntary carbon neutral programs: Adoption and firms' strategies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 381:135191, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135191.
- E. Babakus and G. Mangold. Adapting the servqual scale to hospital services: An empirical investigation. *Health Service Research*, 26:767–780, 1992.
- A. Baranzini, N. Borzykowski, and S. Carattini. Carbon offsets out of the woods? acceptability of domestic vs. international reforestation programmes in the lab. *ournal of Forest Economics*, 32:1–12, 2018. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFE.2018.02.004>.
- M. Bech and D. Gyrd-Hansen. Effects coding in discrete choice experiments. *health economics*. *Health Economics*, 14(10):1079—1083, 2005. URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/HEC.984>.
- J. Blasch and M. Farsi. Context effects and heterogeneity in voluntary carbon offsetting—a choice experiment in Switzerland. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 3(1):1–24, 2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2013.842938>.
- S. Bresciani, S. U. Rehman, G. Giovando, and G. M. Alam. The role of environmental management accounting and environmental knowledge management practices influence on environmental performance: mediated-moderated model. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 27(4):896–918, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-12-2021-0953>.
- J. Busch, J. J. Bukoski, S. C. Cook-Patton, B. Griscom, D. Kaczan, M. D. Potts, Y. Yi, and J. R. Vincent. Cost-effectiveness of natural forest regeneration and plantations for climate mitigation. *Nature Climate Change*, 14(9):996–1002, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-02068-1>.
- G. Cevallos, J. Grimault, and V. Bellasse. Domestic carbon standards in Europe Overview and perspectives. Technical Report December, Institute for Climate Economics, 2019.

- Y. Chen, W. Li, J. Liu, and Y. Yang. Effects of water conveyance embankments on riparian forest communities at the middle reaches of the Tarim River, Northwest China. *Ecohydrology*, 6:937–948, 2013. ISSN 19360584. doi: 10.1002/eco.1418.
- J. Cohen. A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112(1):155–159, 2022. URL <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.112.1.155>.
- T. Daddi, N. Todaro, M. D. Giacomo, and M. Frey. A systematic review of the use of organization and management theories in climate change studies. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(4):456–474, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2015>.
- S. Donofrio, P. Maguire, and K. Myers. Buyers of Voluntary Carbon Offsets, a Regional Analysis. Technical report, Ecosystem Marketplace, 2021. URL <https://www.ecosystemmarketplace.com>.
- R. East. Investment decisions and the theory of planned behaviour. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 14(2):337–375, 1993. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-4870\(93\)90006-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-4870(93)90006-7).
- D. Engler, G. Gutsche, A. Simixhiu, and A. Ziegler. On the relationship between corporate CO2 offsetting and pro-environmental activities in small- and medium-sized firms in Germany. *Energy Economics*, 118, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2022.106487>.
- S. Evro, B. A. Oni, and O. S. Tomomewo. Global strategies for a low-carbon future: lessons from the US, China, and EU’s pursuit of carbon neutrality. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 461:142635, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142635>.
- S. Fawzy, A. I. Osman, J. Doran, and D. W. Rooney. Strategies for mitigation of climate change: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 18:2069–2094, 2020. doi: 10.1007/s10311-020-01059-w.
- C. Fornell and D. F. Larcker. Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1):39–50, 1981. URL <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>.
- G. Franke and M. Sarstedt. Heuristics versus statistics in discriminant validity testing: A comparison of four procedures. *Internet Research*, 29(3):430–447, 2019. doi: 10.1108/IntR-12-2017-0515.
- D. L. Gadenne, J. Kennedy, and C. McKeiver. An empirical study of environmental awareness and practices in smes. *Journal of Business Ethics* (, 84:45–63, 2009. doi: 10.1007/s10551-008-9672-9.
- Q. Grafton, H. L. Chu, and H. Nelson. A global analysis of the cost-efficiency of forest carbon sequestration. *OECD Environment Working Papers*, 185, 2021.
- J. F. Hair, M. Risher, J. J. and Sarstedt, and C. M. Ringle. When to use and how to report the results of pls-sem. *European Business Review*, 31(1):2–24, 2019. URL <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203/FULL/XML>.
- N. L. Harris, D. A. Gibbs, A. Baccini, R. A. Birdsey, S. de Bruin, M. Farina, L. Fatoyinbo, M. C. Hansen, M. Herold, R. A. Houghton, P. V. Potapov, D. R. Suarez, R. M. Roman-Cuesta, S. S. Saatchi, C. M. Slay, S. A. Turubanova, and A. Tyukavina. Global maps of twenty-first century forest carbon fluxes. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(3):234–240, 2021. doi: 10.1038/s41558-020-00976-6.
- J. O. Haug and I. Hassinggaard. Young consumers’ attitudes towards voluntary carbon offsetting. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(6):2806–2816, 2023.

- B. K. Haya, T. Bernard, A. Abayo, X. Rong, I. S. So, and M. Elias. Voluntary Registry Offsets Database v2025-06, Berkeley Carbon Trading Project, University of California, Berkeley., 2025. URL <https://gspp.berkeley.edu/berkeley-carbon-trading-project/offsets-database>.
- J. Henseler, C. M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt. A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1):115–135, 2015. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11747-014-0403-8>.
- D. A. Hensher, C. Ho, and C. . Mulley. Identifying preferences for public transport investments under a constrained budget. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 72:27–46, 2015. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRA.2014.12.002>.
- D. Hoyos. The state of the art of environmental valuation with discrete choice experiments. *Ecological economics*, 69(8):1595–1603, 2010. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2010.04.011>.
- INE. Directorio Central de Empresas (DIRCE) a 1 de enero de 2023. Technical report, Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2023. URL https://www.ine.es/prensa/dirce_2023.pdf.
- INE. Directorio Central de Empresas (DIRCE) a 1 de enero de 2024. Technical report, Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2024. URL <https://www.ine.es/dyngs/Prensa/es/DIRCE2024.htm>.
- IPCC. Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Technical report, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA., 2022.
- T. Kautonen, M. Van Gelderen, and E. T. Tornikoski. Predicting entrepreneurial behaviour: a test of the theory of planned behaviour. *Applied economics*, 45(6):697–707, 2013.
- Y. Kim, S. Yun, and J. Lee. Can companies induce sustainable consumption? The impact of knowledge and social embeddedness on airline sustainability programs in the U.S. *Sustainability*, 6:3338–3356, 2014. ISSN 20711050. doi: 10.3390/su6063338.
- I. Krinsky and A. L. Robb. On approximating the statistical properties of elasticities. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 68(4):715–719, 1986.
- D. Laibson and J. A. List. Principles of (behavioral) economics. *American Economic Review*, 105(5):385–390, 2015.
- D.-H. Lee, D.-h. Kim, and S.-i. Kim. Characteristics of forest carbon credit transactions in the voluntary carbon market. *Climate Policy*, 18(2):235–245, 2018. doi: 10.1080/14693062.2016.1277682.
- D. L. Levy. Business and the evolution of the climate regime: The dynamics of corporate strategies. *The Business of Global Environmental Governance*, pages 73–104, 2004. doi: 10.7551/MITPRESS/1705.003.0009.
- J. Lou, N. Hultman, A. Patwardhan, and I. Mintzer. Corporate motivations and co-benefit valuation in private climate finance investments through voluntary carbon markets. *NPJ Climate Action*, 32, 2023. URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00063-4>.
- H. B. Mann and D. R. Whitney. On a test of whether one of two random variables is stochastically larger than the other. *The annals of mathematical statistics*, pages 50–60, 1947.

- D. McFadden. The measurement of urban travel demand. *Journal of Public Economics*, 3(4):303–328, 1974. URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2727\(74\)90003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2727(74)90003-6).
- D. McFadden and K. Train. Mixed MNL models for discrete response. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 15(5):447–470, 2000. doi: 10.1002/1099-1255(200009/10)15:5<447::AID-JAE570>3.0.CO;2-1.
- C. Merk, U. Liebe, Meyerhoff, and K. Rehdanz. German citizens’ preference for domestic carbon dioxide removal by afforestation is incompatible with national removal potential. *Earth Environment*, 4(1), 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00713-9>.
- MITECO. Spanish Registry of Carbon Footprint Offsetting and CO₂ Removal, 2024. Available at: <https://www.miteco.gob.es>.
- K. Monahan. *How Behavioral Economics Influences Management Decision-Making: A New Paradigm*. Academic Press, 2018.
- B. Morales and P. Ovando. Organisational Attitudes and Preferences Towards Forest Carbon Offsets in Spain’s Carbon Footprint Registry. *Submitted , under review*, 2025.
- N. Nachar et al. The Mann-Whitney U: A test for assessing whether two independent samples come from the same distribution. *Tutorials in quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 4(1):13–20, 2008.
- J. C. Nunnally. *Psychometric theory. First Edition*. McGraw-Hill, 1967.
- P. Ovando. Decoding the Carbon Footprint Registry: Insights into Spain’s Voluntary Climate Disclosure Framework. Internal working paper, Institute of Public Goods and Policies (IPP), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Madrid, Spain, 2025.
- G. Papagiannakis and S. Lioukas. Values, attitudes and perceptions of managers as predictors of corporate environmental responsiveness. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 100:41–51, 2012. ISSN 0301-4797. doi: 10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2012.01.023.
- B. S. Probst, M. Toetzke, A. Kontoleon, L. Díaz Anadón, J. C. Minx, B. K. Haya, L. Schneider, P. A. Trotter, T. A. West, A. Gill-Wiehl, and V. H. Hoffmann. Systematic assessment of the achieved emission reductions of carbon crediting projects. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), dec 2024. doi: 10.1038/s41467-024-53645-z.
- B. W. Ritchie, A. Kemperman, and S. Dolnicar. Which types of product attributes lead to aviation voluntary carbon offsetting among air passengers? *Tourism Management*, 85:104276, 2021.
- S. Roe, C. Streck, M. Obersteiner, S. Frank, B. Griscom, L. Drouet, O. Fricko, M. Gusti, N. Harris, T. Hasegawa, Z. Hausfather, P. Havlík, J. House, G. J. Nabuurs, A. Popp, M. J. S. Sánchez, J. Sanderman, P. Smith, E. Stehfest, and D. Lawrence. Contribution of the land sector to a 1.5 °C world. *Nature Climate Change*, 9(11):817–828, 2019. doi: 10.1038/s41558-019-0591-9.
- W. Ruiting, M. S. Ahmad, J. B. Jamaludin, N. Abd Rahim, S. Y. Wong, J. U. Rehman, L. Kumar, and M. E. H. Assad. A comprehensive bibliometric review of voluntary carbon markets: trends and future directions. *Environmental Research Communications*, 7(4): 042001, 2025.
- M. Sarstedt, C. Ringle, and J. Hair. *Handbook of Market Research*, chapter Partial least squares structural equation modeling, pages 1–47. Springer International Publishing, 2021.

- J. Schleich and S. Alsheimer. The relationship between willingness to pay and carbon footprint knowledge: Are individuals willing to pay more to offset their carbon footprint if they learn about its size and distance to the 1.5° c target? *Ecological Economics*, 219: 108151, 2024.
- P. Shashi, C., R. Cerchione, and D. Jhamb. Double-edged circularity: Comparative assessment of circular and non-circular consumers. *Ecological Economics*, 212:107931, 2023. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLECON.2023.107931>.
- P. Slovic. Perception of risk. *Science*, 236(4799):280—285, 1987. URL <https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.3563507>.
- Y. Tao, M. Duan, and Z. Deng. Using an extended theory of planned behaviour to explain willingness towards voluntary carbon offsetting among chinese consumers. *Sustainability*, 2021. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107068>.
- D. W. Thompson and E. N. Hansen. Institutional pressures and an evolving forest carbon market. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 21(6):351–369, 2012.
- F. Tilley. Small firm environmental ethics: how deep do they go? *Business ethics: A European review*, 9:31–41, 2000. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8608.00167>.
- K. Train. *Discrete Choice Methods with Simulation*. Cambridge Press University, 2003.
- K. Train. *Discrete choice methods with simulation, second edition*, volume 9780521766555. Cambridge University Press, 2009. doi: 10.1017/CBO9780511805271.
- N. Triana and T. Ota. Assessing preferences dor forest carbon credit and co-benefits: A choice experiment case in japan. *Environmental Challenges*, 15:100936, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.envc.2024.100936.
- M. D. Wani, S. N. Dar, and P. P. Mohanty. Integrating the Value Belief Norm Theory and Theory of Planned Behavior to Predict the Climate Change Mitigation and Adaption Behaviors in Agriculture Production. *Environmental Management*, pages 1–15, 2025.
- J. Warburg, B. Frommeyer, J. Koch, S.-O. Gerdt, and G. Schewe. Voluntary carbon offsetting and consumer choices for environmentally critical products—An experimental study. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(7):3009–3024, 2021.
- World Bank. *State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2025*. The World Bank, 2025. URL <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/39796>.
- C. Wright and D. Nyberg. Corporations and climate change: An overview. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 15(6):e919, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.919>.
- M. Xie and L. Chen. Private Governance in Climate Mitigation: A Global Comparison of Corporate Participation in Voluntary Carbon Markets. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 27(3):245–264, 2025. doi: 10.1080/13876988.2025.2510596.
- C.-H. Yeh, M. Hartmann, M. Gorton, B. Tocco, V. Amilien, and K. K. Steinnes. Looking behind the choice of organic: A cross-country analysis applying integrated choice and latent variable models. *Appetite*, 167:105591, 2021. ISSN 0195-6663. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2021.105591>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0195666321004980>.
- S. Yunus, E. Elijido-Ten, and S. Abhayawansa. Determinants of carbon management strategy adoption. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 31, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-09-2014-1087>.

- A. Yuriev, M. Dahmen, P. Paillé, O. Boiral, and L. Guillaumie. Pro-environmental behaviors through the lens of the theory of planned behavior: A scoping review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 155:104660, 2020. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104660>.
- A. Zhang, H. L. Tay, M. F. Alvi, K. X. Wang, and Y. Gong. Carbon neutrality drivers and implications for firm performance and supply chain management. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(4):1966–1980, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3230>.

Appendix

A.1 Survey Statements and References

Table A1: Common TPB Statements Included in the Survey of Registry and Non-Registry Firms, with Reference Source

Variable	Question	Reference
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm's net-zero efforts	SDS
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	SDS
ATT3	Improves firm's corporate image.	Adapted from (Chen et al., 2013)
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	SDS
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	SDS
PBC2	Is essential to achieve firm's net-zero goal	SDS
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information to offset its carbon footprint with absorption projects	Adapted from (Tao et al., 2021)
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050	Adapted from (Thompson and Hansen, 2012)
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	SDS
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	SDS
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	SDS
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	SDS
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting	Adapted from (Kim et al., 2014)
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting	Adapted from (Tao et al., 2021)
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	Adapted from (Thompson and Hansen, 2012)
OutOffset	1 = Acquisition of carbon offsets outside the Registry; 0 = No offsets acquired outside the Registry	Survey
Awareness	1 = Previous knowledge of the Registry; 0 = No previous knowledge of the Registry	Survey
PastBehaviour	1 = Acquisition of carbon offsets within the Registry ; 0 = No offsets acquired within the Registry	Registry public data

Note: SDS refers to self-developed statements, formulated on the basis of interviews with stakeholders, and tailored to capture aspects specific to this study.

A.2 TPB and Measurement Model Results

Table A2: Descriptive Statistics for TPB Constructs: Registry and Non-Registry Firms

Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	Median	Min	Max	Skew	Kurtosis
Registry firms								
ATT1	213	3.901	0.786	4	1	5	-0.929	1.474
ATT2	213	3.723	0.826	4	1	5	-0.602	0.883
ATT3	213	4.131	0.695	4	1	5	-0.936	2.290
ATT4	213	3.808	0.743	4	1	5	-0.570	0.697
RSK1	213	2.653	0.972	3	1	5	-0.032	-0.428
RSK2	213	3.066	1.062	3	1	5	0.034	-0.772
RSK3	213	3.089	0.915	3	1	5	0.045	-0.101
RSK4	213	3.582	0.966	4	1	5	-0.372	-0.229
PBC1	213	3.085	0.897	3	1	5	0.030	-0.509
PBC2	213	3.864	0.944	4	1	5	-0.732	0.285
PBC3	213	3.089	1.131	3	1	5	-0.019	-0.941
PBC4	213	3.038	1.132	3	1	5	-0.151	-0.700
SN1	213	3.681	0.982	4	1	5	-0.732	0.370
SN2	213	3.667	0.925	4	1	5	-0.509	0.023
SN3	213	3.310	0.965	3	1	5	-0.334	0.058
DecIntention	213	0.432	0.497	0	0	1	0.273	-1.935
PastOffset	213	0.244	0.431	0	0	1	1.183	-0.604
Non-Registry firms								
ATT1	309	3.586	0.881	4	1	5	-0.687	3.963
ATT2	309	3.709	0.879	4	1	5	-0.633	3.663
ATT3	309	3.544	0.909	4	1	5	-0.530	3.444
ATT4	309	3.686	0.831	4	1	5	-0.448	3.548
PBC1	309	2.796	0.964	3	1	5	0.002	3.078
PBC2	309	3.353	0.858	3	1	5	-0.248	3.415
PBC3	309	2.324	1.110	2	1	5	0.376	2.368
PBC4	309	2.440	1.176	2	1	5	0.364	2.275
RSK1	309	2.777	1.071	3	1	5	-0.102	2.491
RSK2	309	2.751	1.142	3	1	5	0.105	2.400
RSK3	309	2.793	0.965	3	1	5	0.011	3.067
RSK4	309	3.249	1.035	3	1	5	-0.089	2.770
SN1	309	3.311	0.883	3	1	5	-0.306	3.305
SN2	309	3.236	0.900	3	1	5	-0.266	3.325
SN3	309	3.000	0.826	3	1	5	-0.345	3.826
DecIntention	309	0.094	0.292	0	0	1	2.772	5.702
Awareness	309	0.482	0.500	0	0	1	0.701	-2.001

Table A3: Cross loadings Stage 1

Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Registry firms¹					
ATT1	0.7985	0.1717	0.2845	-0.2246	0.1875
ATT2	0.7234	0.1814	0.2247	-0.1129	0.2150
ATT3	0.6559	0.4504	0.3549	-0.1008	0.2468
ATT4	0.7596	0.1930	0.2661	-0.1385	0.1491
SN1	0.3326	0.8391	0.2868	-0.2803	0.2470
SN2	0.3268	0.8415	0.4067	-0.1951	0.2559
SN3	0.1583	0.7624	0.3637	-0.1502	0.2309
PBC1	0.3264	0.2579	0.4778	-0.1385	0.1015
PBC2	0.3987	0.4376	0.5599	-0.1144	0.1900
PBC3	0.2166	0.3142	0.8567	-0.1410	0.4147
PBC4	0.1819	0.1671	0.6992	-0.1029	0.1970
RSK1	-0.1449	-0.0749	-0.0403	0.4733	-0.0589
RSK2	-0.2036	-0.2851	-0.2398	0.8183	-0.0843
RSK3	-0.1237	-0.1613	-0.0865	0.7698	-0.2223
RSK4	-0.0438	-0.1130	-0.0587	0.6801	-0.0968
Offset	0.2476	0.2393	0.3181	-0.1273	0.8230
DecIntention	0.1993	0.2531	0.3093	-0.1541	0.8158
Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Non-Registry firms²					
ATT1	0.8257	0.3539	-0.0615	-0.2370	0.0739
ATT2	0.8223	0.3309	-0.0883	-0.1945	0.1469
ATT3	0.6301	0.6417	0.1034	-0.0573	0.2348
ATT4	0.7779	0.2129	0.0046	-0.1250	0.1469
SN1	0.5247	0.9182	0.0887	-0.0825	0.2242
SN2	0.3846	0.8585	0.0788	-0.0448	0.1793
SN3	0.3139	0.7311	0.1400	-0.0219	0.1127
PBC1	-0.1808	-0.0637	0.8939	0.8852	0.0405
PBC2	0.4366	0.5688	0.0678	-0.1090	0.1743
PBC3	0.2575	0.2962	0.4610	0.0500	0.2667
PBC4	0.2269	0.2755	0.3921	-0.0005	0.1653
RSK1	-0.0198	0.1218	0.3049	0.4947	-0.0745
RSK2	-0.2528	-0.0703	0.5475	0.8263	-0.0131
RSK3	-0.1837	-0.0582	0.8918	0.8895	0.0388
RSK4	-0.0871	-0.1288	0.4662	0.7306	-0.0482
Awareness	0.1752	0.1430	0.1335	-0.0162	0.7989
DecIntention	0.1243	0.1930	0.1040	-0.0035	0.7493

Notes: ¹ PBC2 has a higher load in other construct, as does ATT4. We delete them and check how the rest behaves. ² ATT3 and PBC2 have higher loads in other constructs, proposed for deletion.

Table A4: Cross loadings Stage 2

Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Registry firms¹					
ATT1	0.8358	0.1719	0.2384	-0.2223	0.1885
ATT2	0.7729	0.1815	0.1783	-0.1124	0.2163
ATT4	0.7980	0.1931	0.2210	-0.1388	0.1493
SN1	0.2358	0.8394	0.2045	-0.2792	0.2471
SN2	0.2356	0.8419	0.3247	-0.1936	0.2560
SN3	0.0688	0.7618	0.3062	-0.1456	0.2301
PBC1	0.3340	0.2580	0.4565	-0.1336	0.1029
PBC3	0.1806	0.3141	0.9092	-0.1386	0.4151
PBC4	0.1446	0.1671	0.7483	-0.1033	0.1948
RSK1	-0.1355	-0.0750	-0.0484	0.4751	-0.0577
RSK2	-0.1958	-0.2851	-0.2155	0.8031	-0.0842
RSK3	-0.1342	-0.1614	-0.0933	0.7859	-0.2221
RSK4	-0.0673	-0.1131	-0.0317	0.6814	-0.0971
Offset	0.2357	0.2393	0.3046	-0.1299	0.8305
DecIntention	0.1411	0.2530	0.3088	-0.1571	0.8080
Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Non-Registry firms²					
ATT1	0.8491	0.3540	-0.0819	-0.2376	0.0753
ATT2	0.8682	0.3304	-0.1038	-0.1946	0.1481
ATT3	0.6301	0.6417	0.1034	-0.0573	0.2348
ATT4	0.8169	0.2126	-0.0125	-0.1252	0.1475
SN1	0.3799	0.9177	0.0560	-0.0831	0.2220
SN2	0.2775	0.8575	0.0504	-0.0456	0.1774
SN3	0.2113	0.7337	0.1134	-0.0225	0.1141
PBC2	0.4366	0.5688	0.0678	-0.1090	0.1743
PBC3	0.2575	0.2967	0.4507	0.0498	0.2690
PBC4	0.2071	0.2755	0.3803	-0.0009	0.1665
RSK2	-0.2628	-0.0702	0.5548	0.8261	-0.0145
RSK3	-0.2078	-0.0580	0.8998	0.8907	0.0385
RSK4	-0.0976	-0.1289	0.4743	0.7314	-0.0463
Awareness	0.1423	0.1430	0.1311	-0.0157	0.8166
DecIntention	0.0786	0.1925	0.0900	-0.0033	0.7290

Notes: ¹ Risk 1 has a low load and PBC1 has a low load and a higher cross loading, proposed for deletion. ² Risk1 has a low load. PBC has a low load as well as a high cross loading. Both proposed for deletion

Table A5: Cross loadings Stage 3

Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Registry firms¹					
ATT1	0.8408	0.1718	0.1841	-0.2147	0.1880
ATT2	0.7678	0.1815	0.1132	-0.0945	0.2156
ATT4	0.7966	0.1930	0.1514	-0.1262	0.1492
SN1	0.2360	0.8393	0.1450	-0.2821	0.2471
SN2	0.2352	0.8417	0.2887	-0.1922	0.2559
SN3	0.0685	0.7622	0.2886	-0.1552	0.2306
PBC3	0.1810	0.3141	0.9387	-0.1354	0.4149
PBC4	0.1451	0.1671	0.7935	-0.1156	0.1960
RSK2	-0.1958	-0.2851	-0.1717	0.8055	-0.0843
RSK3	-0.1346	-0.1614	-0.1026	0.8191	-0.2222
RSK4	-0.0682	-0.1130	0.0066	0.7239	-0.0969
Offset	0.2355	0.2393	0.2885	-0.1465	0.8263
DecIntention	0.1409	0.2531	0.3332	-0.1516	0.8124
Variable	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Non-Registry firms²					
ATT1	0.8581	0.3542	0.2111	-0.2826	0.0775
ATT2	0.8549	0.3296	0.1885	-0.1960	0.1499
ATT4	0.8223	0.2120	0.1777	-0.1597	0.1483
SN1	0.3788	0.9167	0.2738	-0.0999	0.2176
SN2	0.2761	0.8557	0.2474	-0.0712	0.1736
SN3	0.2133	0.7384	0.2803	-0.0436	0.1162
PBC3	0.2150	0.2974	0.9690	0.0513	0.2725
PBC4	0.2087	0.2755	0.8556	-0.0135	0.1682
RSK2	-0.2658	-0.0700	0.0456	0.9166	-0.0170
RSK3	-0.2065	-0.0576	0.0291	0.8421	0.0380
RSK4	-0.0987	-0.1290	-0.0246	0.6871	-0.0428
Awareness	0.1410	0.1432	0.2443	-0.0142	0.8463
DecIntention	0.0777	0.1916	0.1398	0.0089	0.6914

Notes: ¹ The resulted model was able to pass the discriminant validity tests. ²: The resulted model was able to pass the discriminant validity tests.

Table A6: Fornell-Larcker Criterion Matrix.

Construct	Type of Firm	Attitudes	Subjective Norms	Perceived B. Control	Risk	Behaviour
Attitudes	Registry	0.869				
	Non-Registry	0.845				
Subjective Norms	Registry	0.224	0.815			
	Non-Registry	0.358	0.840			
Perceived Behav. Control	Registry	0.190	0.295	0.802		
	Non-Registry	0.228	0.311	0.914		
Risk	Registry	-0.190	-0.258	-0.145	0.784	
	Non-Registry	-0.255	-0.090	0.033	0.821	
Behaviour	Registry	0.231	0.300	0.379	-0.182	0.819
	Non-Registry	0.146	0.210	0.266	-0.006	0.773

Note: ¹ The bolded value represents the squared Average Variance Extracted and must be the highest value in each column to confirm discriminant validity, ensuring that each construct is different from the others.

Table A7: Heterotrait-Monotrait Criterion

	Attitudes	S. Norms	PBC	Risk	Behaviour
Registry Firms					
Attitudes	-				
Subjective Norms	0.46	-			
PerceivedBehavC	0.66	0.68	-		
Risk	0.28	0.33	0.26	-	
Behaviour	0.45	0.49	0.63	0.28	-
Non-Registry Firms					
Attitudes	-				
Subjective Norms	0.63	-			
PerceivedBehavC	0.68	0.67	-		
Risk	0.25	0.16	0.67	-	
Behaviour	0.39	0.40	0.61	0.14	-

Note: Discriminant validity was assessed using the heterotrait–monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT), the most reliable criterion according to recent simulation evidence (Henseler et al., 2015). Following standard thresholds (Franke and Sarstedt, 2019), HTMT values below 0.90 were taken as evidence of adequate discriminant validity.

A.3 Random Utility Models

Table A8: WTP mixed logit model

Variable	Registry	Non-Registry
Price	-0.027*** (0.003)	-0.037*** (0.003)
Project	0.129 (0.092)	-0.002 (0.075)
Specie	0.109 (0.090)	0.239*** (0.076)
Location	0.248** (0.096)	0.436*** (0.088)
ASC_accept	-3.858*** (0.508)	1.033*** (0.243)
sd.Project	0.004 (0.180)	0.003 (0.177)
sd.Specie	0.004 (0.167)	0.129 (0.400)
sd.Location	0.280 (0.267)	0.496*** (0.151)
sd.ASC_accept	5.199*** (0.542)	2.895*** (0.266)
Log Likelihood	-290.35	-621.79
McFadden R^2	0.47	0.75
AIC	611.6927	1273.585
BIC	677.6466	1360.433
N ^o observations	552	2416
N ^o respondents	69	302
Halton Draws	1000	700

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Corporate Preferences for Forest Carbon Offsets in Spain: Evidence from Firms
Within and Beyond a Voluntary Climate Disclosure Registry

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Supplementary Materials

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S.1 Supplementary TPB results

S.1.1 Distribution of TPB results for Registry and Non-Registry firms

Figure S1: Comparative Distribution of TPB Statement Responses Across Registry and Non-Registry Firms

S.1.2 Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney Comparison of TPB Results

S.1.2.1 Differences between Registry and Non-Registry firms

Table S1: Registry versus Non-Registry firms

Code	Statement	Non-Registry vs. Registry [‡]	
		Z-value ⁽¹⁾	Direction ⁽²⁾
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm’s net-zero efforts.	-4.561***	↓
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	-0.038	↔
ATT3	Improves firms’s corporate image.	-7.954***	↓
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	-4.521***	↓
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	-12.304***	↓
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm’s net-zero goal.	0.833	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	-9.392***	↓
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	-9.392***	↓
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	1.479	↔
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	-3.037***	↓
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	-3.417***	↓
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	-3.878***	↓
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	2.753***	↑
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	-3.254***	↓
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	-0.848	↔
PO	Firms that have offset their emissions in the past	-22.378***	↓
DI	Firms that declare their intention to offset in the future	-9.866***	↓

Notes:

⁽¹⁾ * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.⁽²⁾ Arrows show changes of category 2 (Non-Registry firms) with respect to category 1 (Registry firms as the reference group), indicating: ↔ : No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑: Significant increase in agreement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓: Significant decrease in agreement ($p \leq 0.05$) with the TPB statements.[‡] Full sample: Registry (N=213), Non-Registry (N=309).

S.1.2.2 Differences according to the awareness of the Registry

Table S2: Firms non-aware versus aware of the existence of the Registry

Code	Statement	Non-aware vs Aware [‡]	
		Z-value ⁽¹⁾	Direction ⁽²⁾
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm's net-zero efforts.	-1.463	↔
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	-2.6152***	↓
ATT3	Improves firms's corporate image.	-3.1629***	↓
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	-2.3916**	↓
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	-0.0599	↔
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm's net-zero goal.	-1.2352	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	-4.5164***	↓
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	-2.6295***	↓
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	1.1436	↔
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	0.7854	↔
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	0.0206	↔
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	0.1046	↔
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	-2.7228***	↓
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	-2.1541**	↓
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	-2.1125**	↓
PO	Firms that have offset their emissions in the past	-0.050	↔
DI	Firms that declare their intention to offset in the future	-3.514***	↓

Notes:

⁽¹⁾ * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$ ⁽²⁾ Arrows show changes of category 2 (not aware respondents) with respect to category 1 (respondent aware of the existence of the Registry as the reference group), indicating: ↔ : No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑: Significant differences increasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓: Significant differences decreasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$).[‡] Includes only respondents from the non-registry firm survey, distinguishing between those who indicated awareness of the Registry (N = 149) and those who reported no prior awareness of the Registry before the survey (N = 160).

S.1.2.3 Differences according to the gender of respondents

Table S3: Male versus Female respondents

Code	Statement	Male vs. Female [‡]	
		Z-value ⁽¹⁾	Direction ⁽²⁾
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm's net-zero efforts.	1.454	↔
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	1.6643*	↑
ATT3	Improves firms's corporate image.	-0.2807	↔
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	-0.2631	↔
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	-2.4264**	↓
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm's net-zero goal.	-1.0336	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	-1.5954	↔
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	-0.6674	↔
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	-2.8972***	↓
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	-2.652***	↓
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	-2.75***	↓
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	0.3917	↔
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	1.4751	↔
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	0.6993	↔
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	1.4705	↔
PO	Firms that have offset their emissions in the past	1.089	↔
DI	Firms that declare their intention to offset in the future	0.155.	↔

Notes:

⁽¹⁾ * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$ ⁽²⁾ Arrows show changes of category 2 (Male respondent) with respect to category 1 (Female respondent as the reference group), indicating: ↔ : No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑: Significant differences increasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓: Significant differences decreasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$).[‡] Includes the full sample of Female respondents: (N=227) and Male ones (N=286).

S.1.2.4 Differences according to the firms' size

Table S4: Medium to large firms (MLF) versus small firms (SF)

Code	Statement	MLF vs. SF [‡]	
		Z-value ⁽¹⁾	Direction ⁽²⁾
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm's net-zero efforts.	3.502***	↑
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	1.635	↔
ATT3	Improves firms's corporate image.	4.731***	↑
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	4.064***	↑
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	5.5520***	↑
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm's net-zero goal.	0.593	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	5.358***	↑
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	6.691***	↑
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	-0.561	↔
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	2.429**	↑
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	0.811	↔
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	2.365**	↑
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	-0.326	↔
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	2.188**	↑
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	-0.457	↔
PO	Firms that have offset their emissions in the past	7.647**.	↑
DI	Firms that declare their intention to offset in the future	4.052**.	↑

Notes:

⁽¹⁾ * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$ ⁽²⁾ Arrows show changes of category 2 (Small firms with 50 or less employees) with respect to category 1 (Medium to large firms. with more than 50 employees, as the reference group), indicating: ↔ : No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑: Significant differences increasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓: Significant differences decreasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$).[‡] Includes the full sample of medium to large firms (N=131) and small firms (N=391).

S.1.2.5 Differences according to sustainability and/or social responsibility (SSR) integration in organizational structure

Table S5: Firms with and without dedicated SSR departments

Code	Statement	With vs. without SSR [‡]	
		Z-value ⁽¹⁾	Direction ⁽²⁾
ATT1	Enhances visibility of firm's net-zero efforts.	3.323***	↑
ATT2	Creates employment opportunities in rural areas.	0.720	↔
ATT3	Improves firms's corporate image.	6.392***	↑
ATT4	Generates market opportunities for environmental service providers.	2.867***	↑
PBC1	Reduces corporate costs of achieving net-zero.	5.141***	↑
PBC2	Is essential for achieving firm's net-zero goal.	1.049	↔
PBC3	The firm has the necessary resources and information needed to offset its carbon footprint.	5.137***	↑
PBC4	The firm has sufficient economic and/or technological capacity to achieve net-zero before 2050.	4.027***	↑
RSK1	Constitutes a high-risk investment due to forest fires and/or climate change.	-0.834	↔
RSK2	Offsetting does not represent a genuine reduction in GHG emissions.	4.073***	↑
RSK3	Offsetting diverts resources that could otherwise reduce corporate carbon footprints.	1.985**	↑
RSK4	Offsetting may generate suspicions of greenwashing.	2.676***	↑
SN1	Our clients value carbon offsetting.	1.041	↔
SN2	Our partners and/or shareholders value carbon offsetting.	3.598	↑
SN3	Other firms in my sector offset their carbon footprints through removal projects.	1.601	↔
PO	Firms that have offset their emissions in the past	8.710***	↑
DI	Firms that declare their intention to offset in the future	3.782***	↑

Notes:

⁽¹⁾ * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$ ⁽²⁾ Arrows show changes of category 2 (firms without SSR departments) with respect to category 1 (firms with dedicated SSR department as the reference group), indicating: ↔ : No significant differences ($p > 0.05$); ↑ : Significant differences increasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$); ↓ : Significant differences decreasing agreement with the TPB statement ($p \leq 0.05$).[‡] Includes the full sample of firms with dedicated sustainability and/or social responsibility departments: (N=135) and firms without such departments in their organizational structure (N=387).

S.2 Random utility models

S.2.1 Multinomial models

Table S6: Baseline multinomial model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.005 (0.051)	0.031 (0.048)	0.013 (0.035)
Specie	0.114** (0.051)	0.029 (0.048)	0.068** (0.035)
Location	0.217*** (0.051)	0.075 (0.048)	0.138*** (0.035)
Price	-0.011*** (0.001)	-0.028*** (0.001)	-0.019*** (0.001)
Log Likelihood	-1100.328	-1276.421	-2444.965
McFadden R^2	0.06	-0.08	0.03
AIC	2208.657	2560.8423	4897.929
BIC	2230.42	2584.094	4423.277
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S7: Multinomial model with TPB constructs

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.003 (0.053)	0.037 (0.054)	0.016 (0.037)
Specie	0.124** (0.053)	0.037 (0.054)	0.080** (0.037)
Location	0.230*** (0.053)	0.088 (0.054)	0.159*** (0.037)
Price	-0.019*** (0.002)	-0.010*** (0.002)	-0.015*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.547*** (0.081)	-1.195*** (0.080)	-1.017*** (0.066)
ASC_Att	0.158*** (0.058)	0.277*** (0.068)	0.203*** (0.044)
ASC_SN	0.152** (0.060)	0.092 (0.066)	0.136*** (0.043)
ASC_PBC	0.301*** (0.056)	0.305*** (0.057)	0.305*** (0.040)
ASC_Risk	-0.081 (0.056)	0.026 (0.053)	-0.027 (0.038)
ASC_Survey			1.386*** (0.076)
Log Likelihood	-1038.28	-1110.61	-2162.19
McFadden R^2	0.06	0.06	0.14
AIC	2094.56	2291.53	4344.39
BIC	2143.53	2291.53	4407.76
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S8: Full multinomial model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.003 (0.053)	0.041 (0.054)	0.016 (0.037)
Specie	0.127** (0.053)	0.040 (0.054)	0.080** (0.037)
Location	0.235*** (0.053)	0.090* (0.054)	0.159*** (0.037)
Price	-0.019*** (0.002)	-0.010*** (0.002)	-0.015*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.426*** (0.138)	-0.194 (0.176)	-0.683*** (0.137)
ASC_Att	0.284*** (0.057)	0.136** (0.065)	0.238*** (0.042)
ASC_SN	0.158*** (0.059)	0.165*** (0.062)	0.165*** (0.042)
ASC_PBC	0.143** (0.057)	0.311*** (0.058)	0.239*** (0.040)
ASC_Risk	-0.068 (0.057)	0.013 (0.054)	-0.020 (0.038)
ASC_< 50 <i>Employees</i>	-0.230** (0.112)	-0.708*** (0.153)	-0.389*** (0.091)
ASC_Service	0.544*** (0.110)	-0.586*** (0.115)	0.016 (0.080)
ASC_SustDepart	-0.067 (0.114)	0.020 (0.158)	-0.017 (0.092)
ASC_Aware			-0.004 (0.087)
ASC_Survey			1.243*** (0.095)
Log Likelihood	-1023.665	-1086.514	-2158.646
McFadden R^2	0.12	0.08	0.14
AIC	2072.56	2189.34	4316.98
BIC	2137.85	2259.1	4405.70
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S9: Service multinomial model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.005 (0.052)	0.040 (0.053)	0.015 (0.037)
Specie	0.121** (0.052)	0.037 (0.053)	0.076** (0.037)
Location	0.227*** (0.052)	0.089* (0.053)	0.154*** (0.037)
Price	-0.019*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.014*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.192** (0.094)	-0.720*** (0.104)	-1.017*** (0.084)
ASC_Service	0.664*** (0.105)	-0.615*** (0.109)	0.071 (0.076)
ASC_Survey			1.338*** (0.075)
Log Likelihood	-1057.61	-1141.8	2245.6
McFadden R^2	0.096	0.030	0.105
AIC	2127.21	2295.53	4505.16
BIC	2159.86	2330.40	4549.52
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S10: PYME multinomial model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.005 (0.052)	0.038 (0.053)	0.015 (0.037)
Specie	0.118** (0.052)	0.037 (0.053)	0.077** (0.037)
Location	0.220*** (0.052)	0.087 (0.053)	0.154*** (0.037)
Price	-0.018*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.014*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.561*** (0.094)	-0.295** (0.138)	-0.619*** (0.097)
ASC_< 50 <i>Employees</i>	-0.080 (0.103)	-0.981*** (0.137)	-0.398*** (0.084)
ASC_Survey			1.170*** (0.080)
Log Likelihood	-1077.7	-1133.43	-2234.95
McFadden R^2	0.078	0.037	0.109
AIC	2167.39	2278.86	4483.9
BIC	2200.035	2313.74	4528.26
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S11: Sustainability multinomial model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.005 (0.051)	0.037 (0.053)	0.015 (0.037)
Specie	0.118** (0.052)	0.036 (0.053)	0.076** (0.037)
Location	0.220*** (0.052)	0.087 (0.053)	0.154*** (0.037)
Price	-0.018*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.014*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.542*** (0.099)	-1.222*** (0.081)	-0.993*** (0.065)
ASC_SustDepart	-0.035 (0.104)	0.605*** (0.138)	0.183** (0.084)
ASC_Survey			1.246*** (0.082)
Log Likelihood	-1077.94	-682.62	-514.04
McFadden R^2	0.07	0.02	0.11
AIC	2167.88	2308.58	4501.35
BIC	2200.52	2343.46	4545.71
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table S12: Mixed logit models: Simple and WTP specifications

Variable	Registry	Not Registry	Full sample
Project	-0.003 (0.053)	0.041 (0.054)	0.016 (0.037)
Specie	0.127** (0.053)	0.040 (0.054)	0.080** (0.037)
Location	0.235*** (0.053)	0.090* (0.054)	0.159*** (0.037)
Price	-0.019*** (0.002)	-0.010*** (0.002)	-0.015*** (0.001)
ASC_accept	0.375*** (0.107)	-0.183 (0.154)	-0.695*** (0.108)
ASC_Att	0.280*** (0.057)	0.136** (0.065)	0.238*** (0.042)
ASC_SN	0.155*** (0.059)	0.166*** (0.062)	0.164*** (0.042)
ASC_PBC	0.143** (0.057)	0.311*** (0.058)	0.239*** (0.040)
ASC_Risk	-0.073 (0.056)	0.013 (0.054)	-0.021 (0.038)
ASC_PYME	-0.212** (0.108)	-0.716*** (0.142)	-0.384*** (0.086)
ASC_Service	0.550*** (0.110)	-0.588*** (0.114)	0.018 (0.079)
ASC_Survey			1.240*** (0.083)
Log Likelihood	-1023.84	-1086.52	-2158.67
McFadden R^2	0.12	0.08	0.14
AIC	2069.68	2195.05	4341.33
BIC	2129.53	2258.99	4417.38
N ^o observations	1704	2472	4176
N ^o respondents	213	309	522

Notes: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors in parentheses.

S.2.2 Mixed logit models

Table S13: Simple mixed logit model

Variable	Registry	Not Registry
Project	-0.002 (0.075)	0.129 (0.092)
Specie	0.239*** (0.076)	0.109 (0.090)
Location	0.436*** (0.088)	0.248** (0.096)
Price	-0.037*** (0.003)	-0.027*** (0.003)
ASC.accept	1.033*** (0.243)	-3.858*** (0.508)
sd.Project	0.003 (0.177)	0.004 (0.180)
sd.Specie	0.129 (0.400)	0.004 (0.167)
sd.Location	0.496*** (0.151)	0.280 (0.267)
sd.ASC.accept	2.895*** (0.266)	5.199*** (0.542)
Log Likelihood	-813.21	-654.46
McFadden R^2	0.30	0.44
AIC	1644.41	1326.91
BIC	1693.38	1379.23
N ^o observations	1704	2472
N ^o respondents	213	309
Halton Draws	800	700

Notes: * p-value < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, and *** p < 0.01.
Standard errors in parentheses. Standard errors are shown in parentheses.